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QORASUV KANALIDA UNIONIDAE VA CORBICULIDAE OILALARI IKKIPALLALI MOLLYUSKALARINING BIOTOPLARDA TARQALISHI

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Аннотация: В результате проведенных исследований на канале установлено, что распространены 2 семейства, 8 видов, относящихся к 4 родам и 2 подвидам. Установлено, что *Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis* являются редкими стенабионтами, а *Sinanodanta gibba*, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*, *Colletopterium ponderosum volgensis*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*, *Corbiculinaferghanensis* являются обычными. виды эврибионтов. По распределению установлено, что 2 типа по 20% встречаются на каменистых почвах, 3 типа по 30% на песчаных почвах и 5 типов по 50% на глинистых почвах.

Ключевые слова. *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis*, виды, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*.

Abstract: As a result of the conducted research on the channel, it was established that 2 families, 8 species belonging to 4 genera and 2 subspecies are widespread. It was established that *Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis* are rare stenabionts, and *Sinanodanta gibba*, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*, *Colletopterium ponderosum volgensis*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*, *Corbiculinaferghanensis* are common species of eurybionts. According to the distribution, it was established that 2 types are found on stony soils by 20%, 3 types by 30% on sandy soils and 5 types by 50% on clay soils.

Keywords. *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis*, species, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*.

Kirish. Suv ekotizimlarida abiotik va antropogen ta'sirlarga beriluvchan gidrobiontlarning tur tarkibini aniqlash, tarqalishini baholash muxim masalalardan biri bo'lib hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda ichki suv havzalaridagi gidrobiontlar turlari inventarizatsiyalandi, ularni ro'yhatga olishning xalqaro ma'lumotlar bazasi yaratildi, iqtisodiy samarador turlari ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlariga joriy etilmoqda. Aytish lozimki, qurg'oqchil hududlardagi yirik suv havzalarida tarixan shakllangan ikkipallali, qorinoyoqli mollyuskalar, qisqichbaqalar va zuluklar turlarining yashovchanligi daryo suvlarining mavsumiy gidrologik rejimi va fizik-kimyoviy xususiyatlarining o'zgarishiga bog'liqligi o'rganildi [2,4,7,8,10,11]. Bugungi kunda Qorasuv kanalida Unionidae va Corbiculidae oilalari ikkipallali mollyuskalarining biotoplarda tarqalishini o'rganish dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlarning tahlili. Ikkipallali mollyuskalarning sistematikasi, tur tarkibi, ekologik guruhlari va tarqalishi bo'yicha James H.T., S. Alanp (1991), D.C Aldridge (1999), P. Bouchet (2007), Huber Markus (2010,2011), A.E Bogan (2010), Annabelle Cuttelod et al. (201), Maria Haws (2002,2004), N .Mamangkey et al (2009), Sata Yoshida et al. (2013) A.L. Rijnashvili (2009, 2012), Attrill M.J., Depledge M.H.(1997), Gerhardt A. (2000), Borcherdig J.(2006), Kholodkevich S., Sharov A., Nikolić M., Joksimović A. (2015), Izzatullaev Z (2020,2024), Boymurodov X. (2021,2023,2024)lar tamonidan tahlil qilingan [1,3,4,5,6,9,12].

Tadqiqot materiali va metodlari. Material terishda Rijnashvili (2005); Storobogatov, Izzatullaev (1985,1989), Izzatullaev, Boymurodov, (2019, 2023) metodlaridan foydalanildi.

Materiallar Qorasuv kanalidan terildi. Gidrobiontlarning biotoplarda tarqalishi va populyatsiyalarini o'rganishda AlyoxinaG.P., Misetov I.A., Puzakkova M.V, 2007, Izzatullaev Z.I. (2019, 2022), Boymurodov X.T.(2021, 2023) uslublari bilan o'rganildi [2,9,10,11].

Tahlil va natijalar. Qorasuv kanali — Chirchiq daryosining chap sohilidan suv oladi va Toshkent viloyatini suv bilan ta'minlashda muxim ahamiyatga ega. Yuqori Chirchiq gidrouzelidan boshlanadi uzunligi 88,1 km. Suv o'tkazish imkoniyati 179,9 m³/s. Kanal Toshkent viloyatidagi 171,2 ming ga yerni sug'oradi, kanalga ko'pgina soy suvlari ham qo'shiladi. Kanalga Samsaraksoy, Qizilsoy. Juzuruqsoy va Parkentsoylar o'z suvini quyadi. Qorasuv kanali qadimiy kanallardan bo'lib hisoblanadi. Kanalning suvining bir qismi Tuyabo'g'iz suv omboriga quyiladi, bu kanaldan Toshkent kanali ham suv oladi. Kanalda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasida 2 oila, 4 urug'ga kiruvchi 8 tur va 2 kenja turning tarqalganligini aniqladik (1-jadval).

Kanalning yozda tiniqligi o'rtacha 0,47-0,54 m., oqim tezligi 0,57-0,69 m/sek. suv xarorati 14-26⁰S va kuzda tiniqligi 0,61-0,72 m, oqim tezligi 0,33-0,46 m/sek., suv xarorati 12-19⁰S oralig'ida bo'lgan joylarda Unionidae oilasidan *Sinanodonta gibba* 0,6, *Sinanodonta ruerorum* 0,4, *Sinanodonta orbicularis* 0,8, *Colletopterum* urug'idan *Colletopterium bactrianum* 0,5, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum* 0,3 va *Colletopterium ponderosum volgense* 0,8 tarqalganligi aniqlandi.

1-jadval

Qorasuv kanalida Unionidae va Corbiculidae oilalari ikkipallali mollyuskalarining biotoplarda tarqalishi va ekologik guruhlari (n= 10, m²/dona)

№	Turlar	Qorasuv	Ekologik guruhlari
	(Bivalvia) sinfi Unionidae oilasi		
E.1	<i>Sinanodonta gibba</i>	0,6±0,1	Peloreofil
E.2	<i>Sinanodonta ruerorum</i> *	0,4±0,1	Peloreofil
E.3	<i>Sinanodonta orbicularis</i> *	0,8±0,1	Peloreofil
S.4	<i>Colletopterum bactrianum</i> *	0,5±0,1	Reofil
S.5	<i>Colletopterum cyreum sogdianum</i>	0,3±0,1	Reofil
E.6	<i>Colletopterum ponderosum volgense</i>	0,8±0,1	Pelolimnofil
	Corbiculidae oilasi		
S.7	<i>Corbicula cor</i> *	0,2±0,1	Peloreofil
S.8	<i>Corbicula fluminalis</i>	0,3±0,1	Peloreofil
S.9	<i>Corbicula purpurea</i> *	-	Peloreofil
E.10	<i>Corbiculina tibetensis</i>	1,0±0,1	Peloreofil
E.11	<i>Corbiculina ferghanensis</i>	1,1±0,1	Peloreofil
	Jami turlar soni	10	

Yuqorida tarqalish zichligi taxlil qilingan turlar katta ikkipallali mollyuskalar bo'lib ularning uzunligi 19-24 sm. bu turlarning zichligi daryo va suv omborlarga qaraganda kichik ko'rsatkichni ko'rsatadi. Sababi kanal suv satxining o'zgarishi va kanalning ba'zi qismlari betonlashtirilganligi turlar tarqalishiga cheklovchi faktor sifatida o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi.

Kanalning Chirchiq daryosidan suv olishi bu daryoda tarqalgan Corbiculidae oilasi turlarning kanal biotoplarida tarqalishiga olib kelgan lekin ikkala suv tipidagi turlarning zichligi farqlari kuzatiladi. Masalan *Corbicula cor* daryoda 0,4, kanalda 0,2 tada, *Corbicula fluminalis* daryoda 0,6, kanalda 0,3 tada, *Corbiculina* urug'idan *Corbiculina tibetensis* daryoda 1,3, kanalda 1,0 tada, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* daryoda 1,6, kanalda 1,1 tada uchrashi aniqlandi. Bu oila turlari uchun kanallarga nisbatan daryolar qulay bo'lgan suv ekotizimi ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Suv ekotizimlarida tarqalgan *Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Corbicula cor*, *Corbicula fluminalis* turlari kam uchraydigan stenabiontlar va *Sinanodonta gibba*, *Sinanodonta ruerorum*, *Sinanodonta orbicularis*, *Colletopterium ponderosum volgense*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* lar esa keng uchraydigan evribiont turlar ekanligi aniqlandi.

Peloreofillar 7 turi 70 % (*Sinanodanta gibba*, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*, *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*, *Corbiculina ferghanensis*), reofillarning 2 turi 20 % (*Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*) va pelolimnofillarning bir turi 10 % (*Colletopterium ponderosum volgense*) yashashi o‘rganildi.

Tarqalishiga ko‘ra toshloq yerlar 2 tur 20 % (*Corbicuila fluminalis*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*), qumloq yerlarda 3 tur 20 % (*Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Corbiculina ferghanensis*) va loylarda 5 tur 44,4 % (*Sinanodanta gibba*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*, *Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Colletopterium ponderosum volgense*) uchradi.

Xulosa. Kanalda o‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasida 2 oila, 4 urug‘ga kiruvchi 8 tur va 2 kenja turning tarqalganligini aniqladik. Suv ekotizimlarida tarqalgan *Colletopterium bactrianum*, *Colletopterium cyreum sogdianum*, *Corbicuila cor*, *Corbicuila fluminalis* turlari kam uchraydigan stenabiontlar va *Sinanodanta gibba*, *Sinanodanta ruerorum*, *Sinanodanta orbicularis*, *Colletopterium ponderosum volgense*, *Corbiculina tibetensis*, *Corbiculina ferghanensis* lar esa keng uchraydigan evribiont turlar ekanligi aniqlandi. Tarqalishiga ko‘ra toshloq yerlar 2 tur 20 %, qumloq yerlarda 3 tur 30 % va loylarda 5 tur 50 % uchradi o‘rganildi.

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